

Case Report: Bilateral Ainhum in a 6-year-old Black African Male Child

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ABSTRACT Background: Ainhum is an uncommon surgical condition and rarer still in children. It is gradually disappearing due to improved socioeconomic condition of the populace. This has consequently led to paucity of literature on the lesion, making it relatively unknown and may be unrecognized by many. This case report describes the clinical features of this relatively uncommon condition occurring in a black African child, in order to facilitate recognition and appropriate management. **Case Summary:** The patient was a 6-year-old child born to a polygamous family, that presented with complaints of bilateral progressive pain and swelling in the 5th little toes for about 5 months. Attendance to other health facilities including traditional medications has not yielded any improvement. A bilateral constriction at the base of both fifth toes was found on examination. A diagnosis of bilateral Ainhum of the 5th digits was made followed by bilateral amputation at the metatarsophalangeal joint after counseling and due investigations. He had uneventful recovery. **Conclusion:** Ainhum may occur in children ultimately leading to mutilation, amputation being the only viable option of treatment. Socio-demographic factors play an important role in the changing pattern of surgical diseases, more ostensibly in Africa, these needs to be considered in the planning of health services.

KEYWORDS Ainhum, child, treatments

Introduction

Ainhum is a clinical entity that presents as a painful constricting groove that appears at the base of the 5th toe ultimately leading to autoamputation.[1] It is of unknown aetiology but is known to occur with a prevalence of 0.015-2% among Africans that walk bare-footed.[2,3] This, however, is a fast disappearing lesion in many Africans and may not be unconnected to changes in socio-economic lifestyles. We, therefore, found this patient remarkable being a child and the importance of highlighting the lesion to enable recognition and proper treatment.

Case report:

AA was a 6-year-old child born to a polygamous family along with six other siblings. The parents are manual workers living in a new high dense settlement in the outskirts of Kano metropolis, Kano, northwestern Nigeria. He started complaining of pain in the left little toe about 5 months earlier, and the mother has rubbed various ointments at the site with some relief. The mother later observed a mild swelling at the head of the toe and narrowing around the base. A similar problem was also noticed in the left little toe. The ailment has progressed and was advised by neighbours to bring the child to the hospital. There was no history of trauma or the use of bangles or ligatures on the toes and has agreed to walk barefooted occasionally. He has enjoyed good health up until the time of presentation, except for occasional intermittent bouts of fever.

Examination revealed a young child, stunted, not pale, anicteric and afebrile. There was bilateral constriction at the base of both fifth toes more on the left than the right with associated distal swelling and tenderness. The fissure at the plantar aspect was clean and not discharging. The remaining toes on both sides were mostly normal.

An assessment of bilateral Ainhum of the 5th digit was made

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Table 1 Timeline Table: (7th March – 15th August 2011)

Dates	Summary of initial and Follow-up visits	Investigations	Interventions
7/3/11	Seen in General out-patient Department. Registration and Consultation	A diagnosis of bilateral wounds of 5th toes was made	Paracetamol, Ampiclox, Referred to Surgical Outpatient Clinic
21/3/11	Seen in Surgical Out-patient Department. Diagnosis of bilateral Ainhum of the 5 th toes was made.	Investigations requested- genotype AA , PCV 32% Haemoglobin 10g/dl, Normocytic, Normochromic, cells.(25/3/11)	Referred to orthopaedic Surgeon for further review with results.
11 /4/11	Seen in an orthopaedic clinic. Investigations reviewed. Parents have no health, insurance	Need, to do a bilateral amputation of the 5 th , toes decided.	Consenting and Counseling was done. Referred to Social Welfare Unit due to financial constraints
13 /4/11	Seen in social welfare	Parents are indigent	Planned to source for funds
4 /7/11	Seen in orthopaedic clinic. Ainhum has progressed. Need a date for the operation.	Packed Cell Volume, Urea and Electrolytes requested.	Money is available for operation in social welfare accounts.
18/7/11	Booked, for Operation on (27th July 2011)	Packed Cell Volume 40%. Urea 5.6mmo/l, Na+130mm/l, K+5.2mmol/l , Cl-100mmol/l, Hco3-26mmol/l (14th July 2011)	Analgesics (paracetamol)
26/7/11	Admitted to Pediatric Surgical Ward. Anesthetic review		
27/7/11	Bilateral Amputation done under General Anesthesia		Diclofenac, Ampiclox
28/7/11	Postoperative condition satisfactory		Medications continued
29/7/11	Discharged Home		On medications
15/8/11	Seen in Orthopedic Clinic. Wound healed.		Advised on wearing shoes, pedicure and nutrition.

(Figure), and baseline investigations were carried out. His FBC, stool microscopy and urine analyses were essentially normal, and genotype was AA. The parents were counselled on bilateral amputation of the little toes, strict adherence to a regular pedicure, wearing of shoes and regular examination of the remaining toes. Regular pedicure was also similarly advised to be carried out in the other siblings. The child had a bilateral amputation of the fifth toes and uneventful recovery.

Figure: Showing bilateral Ainhum of the fifth digits.

DISCUSSION

The changing pattern of surgical conditions in Africa has been documented by many researchers [4,5] many of these Tropical diseases are gradually diminishing in the day to day surgical practice in Africa; instead we now witness increasing incidences of cancer, diabetic extremities, trauma and diseases more related to economic affluence and lassitude.[4] Among these conditions is Ainhum, meaning a fissure in the language of the Nagos tribe of Brazil, though it may be related to ayun, the word for saw in the Yoruba tribe of Nigeria.[6] The term was first used by da Silva Lima in 1867 from Bahia, Brazil.[7] Ainhum, also known as dactylolysis spontanea, is a painful constriction of the base of the fifth toe (most commonly bilateral), frequently followed by spontaneous amputation a few years later. [3,8,11] In black Africans, the incidence is relatively common, with a range of 0.2-2%. In Nigeria, an incidence of 2.48 cases per 1000 males and 1.08 cases per 1000 females, perhaps the highest in the world has been reported. [6] Males were found to be more affected than females (2:1) and occur in the age range of 20-50 years,[12] is rare in children.

The aetiology of Ainhum is not yet understood however repeated trauma from walking barefooted in the tropics, infection, and poor blood supply have been implicated.[1,6,8] The finding of Ainhum to run among family members, highlights the role of genes as important aetiological factors.[13] Dent et al. discussed a genetically caused abnormality of the blood supply to the foot relating to inadequate posterior tibial artery circulation and absence of plantar arch.[14] Although Ainhum affects the fifth toe most commonly, an affectation of fingers with or without the involvement of toes[6] and isolated great toe has also been reported. [10] The pathology involves fibrotic band that develops from a flexural groove and progressively constricts the full circumference of the toe until spontaneous auto-amputation

occurs.[12] Clinically the criteria for diagnosis are; soft tissue constriction, bulbous enlargement of the toes, and thinning or lysis of phalangeal bones.[12] Clinically, Ainhum pass through four successive stages of increasing severity as follows:[15].

Grade I: callus develops, which progresses to a narrow groove or fissure encircling the toe,

Grade II two: The toe becomes globular distal to the groove, associated with arterial narrowing moreover cancelled, bone resorption

Grade III: bone separation at the joint and hypermotility of the toe

Grade IV: bloodless autoamputation of the toe

Plain X-ray is the investigation of choice, it allows for early diagnosis and appropriate staging. X-ray features of Ainhum include; soft tissue swelling of the fifth toe, distal bulbous swelling of the toe, osteolysis of proximal metatarsophalangeal joint and finally auto amputation.[12,16] The occurrence of the condition in people of low socioeconomic class may need further study while suggesting possible malnutrition in this group among other theories of repetitive trauma and vascular ischemia. Incidentally, the majority of cases of Ainhum were described in active young adults, being extremely rare in children, this patient may perhaps have a nutritional or familial baseline predisposition.

The treatment of Ainhum is mainly amputation but may depend on the stage of the disease [15]. Z plasty treats early cases (Grade I and II). This releases the constricting band thereby relieving pain and progression of the disease. Grade III and IV, however, are treated by amputation.[16]. However, other treatments modalities were reported [15, 17, 18]. Among these were intra-lesional corticosteroids and disarticulation at the metatarsophalangeal joint. Amputation was advised in this patient to prevent further suffering, infection and cost of treatment often not readily available especially if it reoccurred or persists.

CONCLUSION:

Socio-demographic factors play an essential role in the changing pattern of surgical diseases. This phenomenon is seen more ostensibly in Africa where there are rapid changes in lifestyle, improvement in nutrition and eradication of infections. These factors need to be considered in the planning of health services. Ainhum is a gradually disappearing condition; failure of early recognition and treatment will lead to mutilation and disfigurement. Availability of affordable footwear at all ages and better education on dietary habits may further decrease the incidence of this mutilating disease.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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